

Measurements and Equation of State Modeling of the Density of Five 1-Alcohols (C6-C10) at Pressures of up to 120 MPa

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Abstract

The density of five 1-alcohols (1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, 1-octanol, 1-nonanol, and 1-decanol) was measured using a vibrating-tube densimeter at pressures up to 120 MPa for temperatures between 298.15 K and 423.15 K. The relative expanded uncertainty of the experimental data is below 0.2 %. The new results significantly extend the available literature data. The density of the five alcohols was modeled using four molecular-based equations of state (EOS), namely PC-SAFT, SAFT-VR Mie, soft SAFT, and CPA. New component-specific EOS models were parameterized for all considered EOS and substances using vapor-liquid equilibrium data from the literature and the density data from this work. The resulting EOS models describe the density with deviations of about 0.2 - 1.5 %. For the thermal second-order derivative properties, the relative deviations were: 10 - 50 % for the isothermal compressibility and 5 - 35 % for the thermal expansion coefficient. Also, the extrapolation behavior of the EOS models was assessed. Overall, the best results were obtained from the SAFT-VR Mie EOS.

Introduction

Linear primary alcohols with carbon backbone lengths between 6 and 10 are important chemicals. For instance, they are utilized as alternative biofuels.¹⁻⁶ They exhibit good combustion characteristics¹ and can be used as additives in biodiesel.^{6,7} This is of particular interest as long alcohols can be produced from biomass.^{2,3} Long chain 1-alcohols are also used as lubricants additives, e.g. in manufacturing processes.⁸⁻¹⁰ Furthermore, they are important chemical intermediates and frequently used as solvents (e.g. for extraction processes) in chemical industry.¹¹⁻¹⁴

The density (at given temperature and pressure) is a basic thermodynamic property and data on the density and derived properties, such as the compressibility and the thermal expansion coefficient, are needed in many engineering tasks.^{15,16} The accurate description of the density is also an important requirement in the development of equations of state (EOS).¹⁷ In many applications, also information on the density at extreme conditions is needed. E.g., pressures up to 250 MPa are reached in injection systems of combustion engines and pressures in lubricated contacts may exceed 1,000 MPa.^{8,18-21} To be able to model such processes accurately, knowledge on the density at such high pressures, where experiments are difficult, is required. As experimental data of the density is often unavailable, especially at extreme conditions, EOS are needed that enable robust predictions.

There are different methods to measure the density at elevated pressure.²²⁻²⁴ Vibrating-tube densimeters are well-established for such measurements as they yield precise results in a wide temperature and pressure range.²⁴⁻²⁶ The density in those devices is calculated from the period of the tube vibrations, which is the primarily measured quantity. This requires, however, a suitable calibration with calibration fluids of known density.²⁷

For predictive modeling of thermodynamic properties, molecular-based EOS are an attractive choice.²⁸⁻³¹ Molecular-based EOS are usually formulated as fundamental equations describing the Helmholtz energy of the studied substance and explicitly account for different types of molecular interactions and molecular architecture. Due to their physical basis,

they often yield reliable predictions for properties at conditions that were not considered in the training of the model.^{32? -35} For the modeling of substances with hydrogen bonding, molecular-based EOS using the statistical association fluid theory (SAFT)^{36,37} are the state of the art. Several molecular-based EOS models comprising SAFT have been proposed in the literature.³⁸⁻⁴¹

In this work, the density of 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, 1-octanol, 1-nonanol, and 1-decanol was measured at temperatures between 298.15 K and 423.15 K and pressures up to 120 MPa with a vibrating-tube densimeter. The experimental results complement and extend the range of existing literature data. Literature data were used to validate the measurement results. The measurements were then used to model the density, the thermal expansion coefficient, and the isothermal compressibility using four molecular-based EOS, namely the PC-SAFT,⁴² the SAFT-VR Mie,⁴¹ the soft SAFT,⁴³ and the CPA EOS.⁴⁰ Therefore, new component-specific models were fitted to experimental data (both from this work and from the literature), which enables a fair comparison.

Experimental Methods

Chemicals and Sample Preparation

The CAS registry numbers, suppliers, and purities of the chemicals used for sample preparation are given in Table 1. All chemicals were used without further purification. Toluene

Table 1: Chemical specifications.

Substance	CAS reg. no.	Supplier	Mole fraction purity ^a	Lot number
toluene	108-88-3	Sigma-Aldrich	99.98 %	MKCF6188
ethanol	64-17-5	Merck Supelco	≥ 99.9 %	K52680280
1-hexanol	111-27-3	ThermoScientific	99.3 %	10238077
1-heptanol	111-70-6	ThermoScientific	99.8 %	10237915
1-octanol	111-87-5	Merck Supelco	99.5 %	K54568191
1-nonanol	143-08-8	TCI	99.7 %	AD6TI
1-decanol	112-30-1	Merck	99.8 %	S7025863

^a As specified by the supplier.

and ethanol were used as calibration fluids for the calibration.

Measurements

The measurements were conducted with a density measuring cell (DMA HPM, Anton Paar) in combination with an evaluation unit (mPDS 5, Anton Paar) for digital data processing. A scheme of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. The setup has two parts: A hydraulic

Figure 1: Scheme of the experimental setup (grey: Hydraulic part, blue: Sample part).

and a sample part, which are separated by a separator piston. The pressure is induced by a hand spindle pump. The pressure in the sample part is measured by a digital pressure transducer from WIKA (S-20) with a standard uncertainty of $u(p) = 0.05$ MPa (specified by the manufacturer). The pressure in the hydraulic part is monitored by an analog pressure gauge. The temperature is measured by a built-in temperature sensor (Pt1000 resistance thermometer from ABB AG) in the measuring cell with a standard uncertainty of $u(T) = 0.1$ K (specified by the manufacturer). All components were chosen to withstand a pressure of at least 140 MPa. To avoid the accidental built-up of higher pressure, safety valves were installed

in both the hydraulic and the sample part (not shown in Fig. 1). For each substance (see Table 1), six isotherms were studied $T / \text{K} \in \{298.15, 323.15, 348.15, 373.15, 398.15, 423.15\}$ at 13 pressures $p / \text{MPa} \in \{0.1, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110, 120\}$. Only liquid states were studied. Hence, combinations that led to solid or gas states were excluded. All samples were degassed by a vacuum pump before loading the system. The evacuation of the sample was conducted in the sample reservoir. The temperature T , the pressure p , and the period τ of the vibrating tube were recorded digitally for two minutes at each state point using this setup. The valve between the densimeter and the sample reservoir was closed during the measurements to reduce external influences, which slightly increased the pressure. Therefore, the target pressure given above was not always met exactly.

To calculate densities from the measured periods, the density measuring cell was calibrated by calibration fluids with known density. Several empirical models for correlating the density have been proposed in the literature.^{44–46} We have used a model proposed by Anton Paar, which describes the relation between the density ρ and the measured period τ , temperature T , and pressure p as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho / \text{kg m}^{-3} = & a_1 + a_2(T/\text{K}) + a_3(p/\text{MPa}) + a_4(T/\text{K})^2 + a_5(p/\text{MPa})^2 \\ & + \left(a_6 + a_7(T/\text{K}) + a_8(p/\text{MPa}) + a_9(T/\text{K})^2 + a_{10}(p/\text{MPa})^2 \right) (\tau / \text{s})^2 \\ & + a_{11}(\tau / \text{s})^4, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $a_1 \dots a_{11}$ are eleven device constants, which were determined by a fit to the measurements of the calibration fluids (which provides ρ, τ, T, p data sets). Ethanol and toluene were used as calibration fluids. The calibration fluids were selected such that their densities cover the complete expected density range of the samples, i.e. one calibration fluid (ethanol) has a lower density and one calibration fluid (toluene) a higher density than the target substances. The density for the calibration fluids was taken from the multi-parameter EOS from Ref. 47 for ethanol and from Ref. 48 for toluene. They are both valid in the entire considered range of conditions. The uncertainties for the density are specified by the developers of the

EOS as $u_r(\rho) = 0.002$ for ethanol⁴⁷ and $u_r(\rho) = 0.002$ for $p \leq 300$ MPa or $u_r(\rho) = 0.005$ else for toluene.⁴⁸ For the conditions considered here, the uncertainties of both EOS are significantly smaller, as shown in the Supporting Information. For both calibration fluids, the density was measured at the state points stated above excluding state points above the boiling temperature at the corresponding pressure ($T \geq 373.15$ K at $p = 0.1$ MPa for ethanol and $T \geq 398.15$ K at $p = 0.1$ MPa for toluene). The parameters of the calibration function $a_1 \dots a_{11}$ were determined from a least squares fit. The relative standard uncertainty of the calibration is estimated to be $u_{\text{cal,r}}(\rho) = 0.0005$.

The overall expanded uncertainty of the density $U_r(\rho)$ with $k = 2$ was calculated from the individual uncertainties⁴⁹ as

$$U(\rho) = k \sqrt{\left(\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T}\right)_{p,\tau} u(T)\right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p}\right)_{T,\tau} u(p)\right)^2 + \left(\left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \tau}\right)_{T,p} u(\tau)\right)^2 + (u_{\text{cal,r}}\rho)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where the coverage factor k was chosen to be 2 throughout this work and $u(\tau)$ is the standard uncertainty of the primary data of the measured period τ . The partial derivatives of the density with respect to temperature, pressure, and period were calculated from Eq. (1). The resulting relative expanded uncertainty is approximately $U_r(\rho) = 0.0016$ in the entire temperature and pressure range.

Computational Methods

Empirical Correlation $\rho(T, p)$

For each studied substance, an empirical correlation of the density data $\rho(T, p)$ was established to evaluate the results and compare them to literature data. Therefore, the polynomial

function $\rho(T, p)$ given in Eq. (3) was chosen based on preliminary tests.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{corr}} / \text{kg m}^{-3} = & c_0 + c_1(T/\text{K}) + c_2(T/\text{K})^2 + c_3(p/\text{MPa}) + \\ & c_4(T/\text{K})^3(p/\text{MPa}) + c_5(T/\text{K})(p/\text{MPa})^3 + c_6(T/\text{K})^2(p/\text{MPa})^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The seven adjustable parameters of Eq. (3) were fitted to the experimental results for each substance individually. Due to their empirical nature, the resulting correlations are not suited for extrapolation beyond the temperature and pressure range of the data to which it was fitted. The parameters are given in the Supporting Information.

The thermal expansion coefficient α and the isothermal compressibility β were computed as

$$\alpha = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_p \quad \text{and} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial p} \right)_T. \quad (5)$$

The thermal expansion coefficient α and the isothermal compressibility β were computed directly from the empirical density model $\rho_{\text{corr}} = \rho_{\text{corr}}(T, p)$, cf. Eq. (3). Both properties were computed for the state points studied experimentally (see above). The data are provided in the Supporting Information. Additionally, the data are compared to literature data in the Supporting Information. The obtained α and β data is referred to as 'pseudo experimental' data in the following. The expanded uncertainty of the derived quantities $U(\alpha)$ and $U(\beta)$ are estimated by error propagation as

$$U(\alpha) = k \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \rho} \right) \rho + \sum_{i=0}^6 \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial c_i} \right) u(c_i)} \quad \text{and} \quad (6)$$

$$U(\beta) = k \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial \rho} \right) \rho + \sum_{i=0}^6 \left(\frac{\partial \beta}{\partial c_i} \right) u(c_i)}, \quad (7)$$

where $u(c_i)$ are the standard errors of the parameter c_i calculated from the results of the lin-

ear regression in Eq. (3).⁵⁰ For 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, 1-octanol, and 1-nonanol, the average uncertainties were calculated to be $U_r(\alpha) = U_r(\beta) = 0.08$. For 1-decanol, the uncertainties are slightly larger with $U_r(\alpha) = 0.12$ and $U_r(\beta) = 0.14$.

Molecular-based Equation of State Modeling

The density, the thermal expansion coefficient, and the isothermal compressibility of the 1-alcohols were modeled using four molecular-based EOS: PC-SAFT,^{38,42} SAFT-VR Mie,⁴¹ soft SAFT,⁴³ and CPA.⁴⁰ The applied EOS are formulated in the molar Helmholtz energy a as function of the temperature and the density, i.e. $a = a(T, \rho)$. The considered molecular-based EOS models are composed of different contributions to the Helmholtz energy as

$$a = a_{\text{id}} + a_{\text{rep}} + a_{\text{disp}} + a_{\text{chain}} + a_{\text{assoc}}, \quad (8)$$

where a_{id} is the ideal gas contribution, a_{rep} and a_{disp} are the contributions due to repulsive and dispersive interactions, respectively, a_{chain} is the contribution due to chain formation, and a_{assoc} represents the associating (H-bonding) interaction. The PC-SAFT EOS and the SAFT-VR Mie employ the hard sphere model from Boublik and Mansoori.^{51,52} Both EOS use a monomer dispersion term specifically designed for the EOS, cf. Refs.⁴² and,⁴¹ respectively. The soft SAFT EOS uses the Lennard-Jones EOS from Johnson et al. as monomer term for modeling the repulsive and dispersive interactions.⁵³ The CPA EOS uses the Soave-Redlich-Kwong EOS as monomer term. All four considered EOS frameworks use versions of the SAFT model proposed by Chapman³⁶ for describing the association. For the chain contribution, the PC-SAFT EOS uses a hard chain reference fluid model from Boublik and Mansoori.^{51,52} The soft SAFT EOS is based on the chain model (describing Lennard-Jones chains) proposed by Johnson et al.⁵⁴ The SAFT-VR Mie EOS chain term is formulated as a model for tangential bonded Mie segment chains.⁴¹ No explicit chain contribution is used in the CPA EOS. For most of the studied alcohols, component-specific models for the four EOS frameworks are

available in the literature.^{55–59} The results using models from the literature are shown and compared in the Supporting Information. Yet, those were parameterized using different reference data sets and fitting methods. To enable a fair comparison of the performance of the EOS frameworks, we developed component-specific models for the five alcohols in this work using the same reference data sets and fitting routines for all EOS frameworks. All models include association by the SAFT term,³⁶ but no polar contributions. The 2B association scheme was applied. The component-specific model parameters were fitted in this work for all five substances using the density results from this work in combination with experimental data from the literature^{55,60–73} for the vapor pressure p^s and the saturated liquid density ρ^s . Only vapor pressure and saturated liquid density data with $T < 0.9T_c$ were used as the critical point is not well described by molecular-based EOS.⁷⁴ The squared relative error was used for the fitting. Details are given in the Supporting Information. For the SAFT-VR Mie, six parameters were used in the models in contrast to only five parameters used for the other three EOS frameworks. The resulting parameters are given in Tables 2 - 5.

Table 2: PC-SAFT component-specific models developed in in this work: The column indicate the segment number m , segment diameter σ , segment dispersion energy ε , association volume κ_{AB} , and association energy ε_{AB} .

Substance	m	$\sigma / \text{\AA}$	$\varepsilon / k_B\text{K}$	$\kappa_{AB} / 10^{-3}$	$\varepsilon_{AB} / k_B\text{K}$
1-hexanol	2.6387	4.0904	296.28	2.2982	2985.1
1-heptanol	3.1386	4.0206	287.29	2.5257	2943.2
1-octanol	3.5238	4.0157	285.27	2.3575	2944.9
1-nonanol	3.9179	4.0033	280.35	2.3733	3010.5
1-decanol	4.3381	3.9888	278.38	2.0959	3018.7

Brown’s characteristic curves⁷⁵ were used to assess the extrapolation behavior of the EOS models. The characteristic curves define lines on the thermodynamic $p\rho T$ surface, along which the compressibility factor Z or its derivatives are identical to the corresponding ideal gas values. Details are given in Refs. 75–77. The thermodynamic definitions of the four curves are given in Table 6. Based on these characteristics, the consistency of EOS can

Table 3: SAFT-VR Mie component-specific models developed in in this work: The column indicate the segment number m , segment diameter σ , segment dispersion energy ε , repulsive exponent λ_r , association radius r_{AB} , and association energy ε_{AB} . The attractive exponent was $\lambda_a = 6$ in all cases.

Substance	m	$\sigma / \text{\AA}$	$\varepsilon / k_B K$	λ_r	r_{AB} / σ	$\varepsilon_{AB} / k_B K$
1-hexanol	2.0411	4.5361	370.31	13.532	0.27932	3192.6
1-heptanol	2.2228	4.6161	406.97	15.566	0.2834	3108.3
1-octanol	2.3588	4.7289	456.3	18.936	0.29574	2912.8
1-nonanol	2.6733	4.66	419.34	16.579	0.28245	3182.2
1-decanol	3.0053	4.6078	407.63	15.97	0.27674	3224.8

Table 4: Soft SAFT component-specific models developed in in this work: The column indicate the segment number m , segment diameter σ , segment dispersion energy ε , association volume κ_{AB} , and association energy ε_{AB} .

Substance	m	$\sigma / \text{\AA}$	$\varepsilon / k_B K$	κ_{AB}	$\varepsilon_{AB} / k_B K$
1-hexanol	3.176	3.8521	276.96	35.46	3279.5
1-heptanol	3.5617	3.8604	280.8	31.755	3254.7
1-octanol	3.8077	3.9316	288.16	21.411	3332.8
1-nonanol	3.8409	4.0513	296.6	14.501	3584.1
1-decanol	4.0642	4.1128	301.34	11.182	3672.3

Table 5: CPA component-specific models developed in in this work: The column indicate the energy parameter α , pseudo critical temperature T_{cm} , pseudo critical pressure p_{cm} , association volume κ_{AB} , and association energy ε_{AB} .

Substance	α	T_{cm} / K	p_{cm} / bar	$\kappa_{AB} / 10^{-3}$	$\varepsilon_{AB} / k_B K$
1-hexanol	0.94524	596.9	38.149	2.0513	2837.7
1-heptanol	0.95308	636.87	35.364	0.92934	3025.8
1-octanol	0.95976	668.74	33.052	0.52529	3217.9
1-nonanol	1.1088	682.79	30.174	0.51068	3093.2
1-decanol	1.1686	706.71	28.578	0.31068	3171

Table 6: Overview of Brown’s characteristic curves including the name, the abbreviation, and the definition.

Name	Abbreviation	Definition
Zeno curve	Z	$Z = \frac{vp}{RT} = 1$
Amagat curve	A	$\left(\frac{\partial Z}{\partial T}\right)_\rho = 0$
Boyle curve	B	$\left(\frac{\partial Z}{\partial 1/\rho}\right)_T = 0$
Charles curve	C	$\left(\frac{\partial Z}{\partial 1/\rho}\right)_p = 0$

be tested.^{78,79} Brown postulated several criteria for the characteristic curves to be thermodynamically consistent.^{75–77,80,81} These criteria were originally derived for simple fluids, i.e. spherical particles with repulsive and dispersive interactions. Yet, it has been shown based on first principle molecular simulation data⁷⁶ that the criteria are applicable to associating, elongated, and polar fluids.^{76,80,81} Therefore, we apply Brown’s test to the 1-alcohol EOS models developed in this work. Yet, successfully passing this test is only a necessary, but not sufficient condition for the models to be thermodynamically consistent.

Evaluation of Models

To quantify the deviations from a given model (empirical correlation or EOS) and experimental data, two deviation measures are used in this work: The average absolute deviation (AAD) and the median absolute deviation (MAD) given as

$$\text{AAD}_{Y,\text{mod}}^{\text{src}} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{exp}}} \sum_i^{N_{\text{exp}}} \left| \frac{Y_{\text{mod},i} - Y_{\text{exp},i}^{\text{src}}}{Y_{\text{exp},i}^{\text{src}}} \right| \quad \text{and} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{MAD}_{Y,\text{mod}}^{\text{src}} = \text{Median} \left\{ \left| \frac{Y_{\text{mod},i} - Y_{\text{exp},i}^{\text{src}}}{Y_{\text{exp},i}^{\text{src}}} \right| \right\}, \quad (10)$$

where $Y_{\text{exp},i}^{\text{src}}$ are the experimental data (source (src) is either this work (th) or literature (lit)) and $Y_{\text{mod},i}$ the corresponding value calculated either from an empirical correlation model (corr), cf. Eq. (3), or an EOS model.

Results and Discussion

Experimental Results

The experimental results for the density of the studied 1-alcohols are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Results for the density measurements for 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, 1-octanol, 1-nonanol, and 1-decanol.

p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
1-hexanol					
$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 323.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 348.15 \text{ K}$	
0.2	815.1	0.14	796.6	0.12	777.4
10.2	821.6	10.19	804.1	10.32	786.1
20.14	827.6	20.21	810.8	20.15	793.5
30.16	833.3	30.31	817.1	30.2	800.5
40.13	838.5	40.24	822.9	40.14	806.9
50.3	843.6	50.29	828.4	50.21	813.0
60.29	848.4	60.26	833.5	60.05	818.5
70.24	852.9	70.25	838.4	70.22	823.9
80.22	857.2	80.28	843.0	80.06	828.9
89.97	861.2	90.12	847.4	90.26	833.8
100.04	865.3	100.17	851.7	100.13	838.3
110.18	869.2	110.1	855.8	110.03	842.7
120.04	872.8	120.07	859.7	120.18	846.9
$T = 373.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 398.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 423.15 \text{ K}$	
0.2	757.3	0.12	734.7	0.3	710.5
10.22	767.1	10.36	746.3	10.32	724.2
20.07	775.7	20.2	756.2	20.3	735.8
30.33	783.7	30.27	765.0	30.33	745.8
40.3	790.7	40.12	772.9	40.11	754.7
50.34	797.4	50.14	780.2	50.25	762.9
60.25	803.0	60.18	787.0	60.25	770.6

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p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
70.2	808.7	70.17	793.3	70.21	777.5
80.23	814.2	80.16	799.2	80.04	783.8
90.1	819.3	90.12	804.8	90.05	789.9
100.24	824.3	100.32	810.2	100.13	795.6
110.01	828.9	110.09	815.2	110.18	801.2
120.08	833.6	120.18	820.1	120.24	806.3
1-heptanol					
$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 323.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 348.15 \text{ K}$	
0.39	819.1	0.32	800.9	0.22	782.1
10.24	825.3	10.44	808.1	10.29	790.3
20.38	831.3	20.25	814.5	20.18	797.5
30.51	836.8	30.24	820.5	30.28	804.3
40.2	841.8	40.28	826.2	40.22	810.5
50.39	846.8	50.29	831.5	50.3	816.4
60.42	851.4	60.4	836.6	60.24	821.8
70.34	855.8	70.47	841.3	70.2	827.0
80.47	860.0	80.3	845.8	80.27	832.0
90.38	864.1	90.24	850.1	90.23	836.6
100.39	868.0	100.27	854.4	100.19	841.1
110.33	871.7	110.37	858.4	110.11	845.3
120.17	875.3	120.07	862.2	120.26	849.5
$T = 373.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 398.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 423.15 \text{ K}$	
0.18	762.3	0.35	740.6	0.26	717.9
10.18	771.6	10.32	751.3	10.3	730.8
20.3	780.0	20.34	760.9	20.16	741.6

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p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
30.33	787.6	30.33	769.4	30.14	751.2
40.18	794.3	40.25	777.1	40.34	760.0
50.2	800.8	50.13	784.1	50.3	767.8
60.17	806.7	60.3	790.7	60.27	774.8
70.33	812.6	70.1	796.7	70.39	781.9
80.28	817.8	80.33	802.7	80.37	788.1
90.2	822.8	90.14	808.1	90.23	793.8
100.42	827.7	100.23	813.2	100.19	799.4
110.3	832.2	110.43	818.2	110.22	804.7
120.3	836.6	120.24	822.8	120.23	809.7

1-octanol

$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$

$T = 323.15 \text{ K}$

$T = 348.15 \text{ K}$

0.15	822.0	0.21	803.8	0.12	785.4
10.14	828.2	10.14	810.7	10.11	793.2
20.14	833.8	20.17	817.0	20.14	800.4
30.24	839.2	30.4	823.0	30.22	807.0
40.38	844.3	40.33	828.5	40.28	813.1
50.26	849.0	50.24	833.6	50.25	818.7
60.31	853.5	60.12	838.4	60.24	824.1
70.32	857.9	70.29	843.2	70.14	829.1
80.3	862.0	80.3	847.7	80.32	834.0
90.25	865.9	90.21	851.9	90.12	838.5
100.26	869.7	100.11	856.0	100.17	842.9
110.19	873.4	110.13	859.9	110.08	847.1
120.1	877.0	120.16	863.7	120.25	851.2

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p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
$T = 373.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 398.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 423.15 \text{ K}$	
0.29	765.9	0.25	745.3	0.17	723.2
10.26	775.2	10.21	755.7	10.17	735.5
20.18	783.1	20.28	764.9	20.11	746.0
30.14	790.4	30.2	772.9	30.24	755.4
40.3	797.3	40.14	780.4	40.37	763.8
50.11	803.3	50.26	787.4	50.11	771.2
60.38	809.4	60.12	793.6	60.05	778.2
70.24	814.7	70.26	799.7	70.48	785.0
80.31	820.0	80.29	805.3	80.32	791.1
90.19	824.9	90.11	810.5	90.16	796.7
100.16	829.6	100.25	815.7	100.22	802.3
110.35	834.2	110.33	820.6	110.33	807.5
120.26	838.4	120.17	825.2	120.29	812.4
1-nonanol					
$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 323.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 348.15 \text{ K}$	
0.17	825.2	0.27	807.6	0.14	789.1
10.14	831.0	10.21	814.3	10.15	796.8
20.1	836.6	20.21	820.5	20.12	803.7
30.29	841.8	30.24	826.2	30.25	810.2
40.16	846.7	40.35	831.6	40.21	816.1
50.24	851.4	50.16	836.6	50.29	821.7
60.22	855.8	60.21	841.4	60.1	826.8
70.35	860.0	70.19	845.9	70.22	831.8
80.24	864.1	80.38	850.4	80.31	836.6

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p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
90.17	867.9	90.3	854.6	90.26	841.1
100.22	871.7	100.25	858.6	100.2	845.3
110.27	875.3	110.36	862.4	110.2	849.5
120.0	878.7	120.22	866.1	120.39	853.5
$T = 373.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 398.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 423.15 \text{ K}$	
0.16	770.3	0.3	750.1	0.17	728.5
10.21	779.0	10.15	760.0	10.28	740.3
20.14	786.8	20.1	768.7	20.37	750.5
30.22	794.0	30.29	776.9	30.22	759.3
40.19	800.6	40.25	784.1	40.18	767.5
50.18	806.7	50.18	790.8	50.28	774.9
60.14	812.4	60.17	797.0	60.2	781.6
70.21	817.8	70.32	802.8	70.13	788.0
80.24	822.8	80.21	808.3	80.31	794.0
90.17	827.7	90.36	813.5	90.22	799.6
100.2	832.3	100.3	818.6	100.12	804.9
110.24	836.7	110.26	823.3	110.38	810.2
120.14	840.8	119.9	827.6	119.96	814.7
1-decanol					
$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 323.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 348.15 \text{ K}$	
0.22	827.2	0.29	810.1	0.16	791.9
10.22	833.0	10.22	816.6	10.17	799.4
20.33	838.5	20.29	822.6	20.11	806.2
30.23	843.6	30.21	828.2	30.26	812.5
40.3	848.4	40.17	833.5	40.19	818.4

Continued on next page

p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	p / MPa	$\rho / \text{kg m}^{-3}$
50.2	853.0	50.32	838.6	50.17	823.8
60.17	857.4	60.35	843.3	60.2	829.0
70.17	861.7	70.19	847.8	70.18	833.8
80.34	865.9	80.24	852.1	80.31	838.5
90.25	869.6	90.2	856.2	89.99	842.8
100.44	873.5	100.27	860.2	100.26	847.2
		110.38	864.0	110.14	851.3
		120.2	867.7	120.22	855.2
$T = 373.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 398.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 423.15 \text{ K}$	
0.2	773.6	0.31	752.4	0.22	729.5
10.18	782.1	10.38	762.6	10.13	740.5
20.23	789.7	20.23	770.7	20.31	750.5
30.28	796.6	30.2	778.3	30.1	759.2
40.29	803.2	40.3	785.8	40.3	767.0
50.37	809.2	50.29	792.3	50.27	774.4
60.29	814.8	60.36	798.4	60.28	781.2
70.3	820.1	70.25	804.1	70.22	787.6
80.28	825.0	80.27	809.6	80.23	793.3
90.15	829.6	90.0	814.7	90.16	798.8
100.21	834.2	100.36	819.6	100.43	804.2
110.39	838.6	110.33	824.4	110.27	808.8
120.1	842.8	120.31	829.0	120.05	814.1

The standard uncertainties of the temperature T and pressure p are $u(T) = 0.1 \text{ K}$ and $u(p) = 0.05 \text{ MPa}$. The combined expanded uncertainties for the density is $U(\rho) = 1.3 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ ($k = 2$).

Fig. 2 shows the measured densities of the five 1-alcohols as a function of the pressure. Also the results from the empirical correlations of the data, cf. Eq. (3), are shown. The density of the 1-alcohols increases with increasing chain length. Only liquid state points were studied, i.e. state points where the sample was (partially) solidified were discarded. This was evidenced by an increased density at these points and an abrupt pressure drop during compression indicating a phase transition. A solidification was observed only for 1-decanol at $T = 298.15$ K and $p \geq 110$ MPa. Both state points are above the measured solidification pressure at this temperature⁸² (see also Supporting Information).

The results from this work were compared to literature data. Refs. 25,62,71,83? –132 report data on the studied 1-alcohols. An overview of the available literature data for each of the five substances is given in the Supporting Information. For 1-hexanol, data are available in the entire range of conditions that were studied in the present work. For the longer 1-alcohols (1-heptanol to 1-decanol), data is sparse. The experimental data from this work significantly extend and complement the available data for these substances.

For comparing the different data sets, the relative deviation between the data and the empirical correlations is used here. The relative deviations of all studied 1-alcohols at ambient pressure are shown in Fig. 3 as a function of the temperature. Overall, the experimental data from this work agree well with the literature data. Most of the literature data deviate not more than $\pm 0.2\%$ from the empirical correlations in the entire temperature range. The experimental data from this work are generally well within the scattering of the literature data from the different groups, especially for lower temperatures, where more experimental data are available.

Fig. 4 shows the relative deviations of the experimental data and the empirical correlations for 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, and 1-octanol as a function of the pressure for the different studied temperatures. Fig. 5 shows the corresponding results for 1-nonanol and 1-decanol. The literature data at elevated pressure scatter more than those at ambient pressure. At temperatures above 348 K, literature data is scarce, especially at high pressures. For 1-

Figure 2: Density ρ of the studied 1-alcohols as a function of pressure p . Symbols: Experimental results from this work; lines: Empirical correlation based on Eq. (3).

Figure 3: Relative deviation between experimental density data at ambient pressure (symbols) and the empirical correlations of the data from this work, cf. Eq. (3), (baseline) as a function of the temperature T . Solid squares indicate results from this work (with error bars $U(\rho)$ ($k = 2$)) and open symbols indicate data from the literature^{25,62,71,83? -132} (symbols are defined according to the legends in Figs. 4 and 5).

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|----------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| ○ Alaoui et al. (2013) | ○ Alaoui et al. (2013) | △ Altunin et al. (1980) |
| ◁ Audonnet and Padua (2002) | ◁ Davila et al. (2012) | ○ Apaev et al. (1987) |
| ▽ Danforth (1931) | ▽ Dzida (2007) | ○ Basu et al. (2014) |
| ■ Domanska et al. (2012) | ○ Garg et al. (1993) | ◁ Davila et al. (2012) |
| ◇ Dubey and Kaur (2013) | ▷ Golubev et al. (1981) | ▽ Dzida (2007) |
| ○ Forghani et al. (2022) | ○ Guzman-Lopez et al. (2017) | ○ Garg et al. (1993) |
| ○ Garg et al. (1993) | ■ Habibullah et al. (2013) | ◇ Guzman-Lopez et al. (2017) |
| ▷ Gylmanov et al. (1979) | ■ Pimentel-Rodas et al. (2016) | ○ Henriques et al. (2020) |
| ■ Henriques et al. (2020) | ◇ Pimentel-Rodas et al. (2019) | ○ Lee et al. (2009) |
| ◇ Iglesias-Silva et al. (2016) | ○ Sanz et al. (2021) | ○ Matsuo and Makita (1989) |
| ◇ Matsuo and Makita (1989) | ○ Shakhverdiev and Bulgan (1998) | ◇ Pimentel-Rodas et al. (2019) |
| △ Randzio et al. (1995) | ◇ Suelzner and Luft (1997) | * Qin et al. (2022) |
| ■ Shakhverdiev et al. (1992) | ○ Uddin et al. (2020) | ■ Sarkoohaki et al. (2018) |
| ○ Troncoso et al. (2003) | ○ Wang et al. (2015) | ○ Sreenivasulu et al. (2014) |
| □ Valencia et al. (2009) | * Wang et al. (2022) | ■ Valero-Hernandez et al. (2022) |
| * Wang et al. (2022) | △ Zuniga-Moreno et al. (2008) | ▷ Zuniga-Moreno et al. (2007) |
| ○ Zuniga-Moreno et al. (2006) | ■ this work | ■ this work |
| ■ this work | | |

Figure 4: Relative deviation between experimental density data (symbols) and the empirical correlations, cf. Eq. (3), (baseline) for 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, and 1-octanol as a function of the pressure p . Solid squares indicate results from this work (with error bars $U(p)$ ($k = 2$)) and open symbols indicate data from the literature. ^{25,62,71,83? -132}

Figure 5: Relative deviations between experimental density data (symbols) and the empirical correlations, cf. Eq. (3), (baseline) for 1-nonanol and 1-decanol as a function of the pressure p . Solid squares indicate results from this work (with error bars $U(\rho)$ ($k = 2$)) and open symbols indicate data from the literature. ^{25,62,71,83? -132}

nonanol and 1-decanol, in general few data are available in literature. The experimental results from this work are in very good agreement with the literature data, especially for 1-hexanol and 1-heptanol. For 1-octanol, the results from this work lie slightly below the majority of the literature data for $T \leq 348.15$ K. However, the deviations are still within the given expanded combined uncertainty ($k = 2$). Also at $T > 373.15$ K, the data from this work agrees well with most of the literature data.

Overall, the experimental data from the literature confirm the experimental results from this work. This is also shown by the $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}$ and $MAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}$ (cf. Eqs. (9) and (10)) between the empirical correlations and the experimental data. The two deviation measures were computed for the two experimental data sets, i.e. the literature data $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}}$ and the data from this work $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}}$. The results for the AAD and the MAD of the five substances are given in Table 8. The empirical correlations describe the experimental results

Table 8: Deviations of the literature data and the measurement data from this work to the empirical correlations (cf. Eq. (3)). The columns indicate (left to right) the substance name, the average deviations $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}}$ as well as the median deviations $MAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}}$ of the literature data, and the average deviations $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}}$ as well as the median deviations $MAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}}$ of the measurement data from this work (cf. Eqs. (9) and (10)).

Substance	$AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}} / \%$	$MAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}} / \%$	$AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}} / \%$	$MAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}} / \%$
1-hexanol	0.16	0.07	0.03	0.03
1-heptanol	0.10	0.04	0.03	0.03
1-octanol	0.07	0.06	0.03	0.03
1-nonanol	0.23	0.13	0.03	0.03
1-decanol	0.14	0.11	0.05	0.05

with relative mean absolute deviation of less than 0.05 %, which is significantly below the expanded uncertainty specified above. The small deviations between the experimental data from this work and the empirical correlations are measures for the accuracy of the empirical correlations, which were fitted to the experimental data from this work alone. With one exception, also both $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}}$ and $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{th}}$, which quantify the deviations of the literature data from the empirical correlations of the present data, are within the expanded uncertainty $U(\rho)$ ($k = 2$) of the present data of 0.16 %. The only exception is the $AAD_{\rho,\text{corr}}^{\text{lit}} = 0.24$ %

obtained for 1-nonanol, which can be attributed to some large outliers in the literature data (see Supporting Information for a discussion). Overall, the values shown in Table 8 confirm the good agreement of the results from this work with the literature data, as already demonstrated in Figs. 3 - 5.

EOS Modeling Results

By using the same fitting procedure and reference data for the different EOS models, a fair comparison of the different EOS frameworks (PC-SAFT, SAFT-VR Mie, soft SAFT, and CPA) is possible. An additional evaluation of component-specific models from the literature for the considered EOS frameworks is given in the Supporting Information. The results of the fit from this work, i.e. the AADs obtained for the vapor pressure, saturated liquid density, and homogeneous state density are reported in Table 9 in the Appendix. The description of VLE properties, i.e. the vapor pressure and the saturated liquid density, is similar for all EOS frameworks. The vapor pressure data are overall described with $\text{AAD}_{p^s, \text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}}$ values of up to around 1 %. The corresponding values for the saturated liquid density are slightly smaller for the PC-SAFT and the SAFT-VR Mie than for the other two EOS. For the soft SAFT and the CPA EOS, the $\text{AAD}_{\rho^s, \text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}}$ is significantly larger with values between 1 % and 2 %. The performance of the EOS models with respect to the density and its derived properties is discussed in detail in the following.

Fig. 6 shows the deviations of the EOS model results from the empirical correlations (cf. Eq. (3)) as a function of the pressure for 1-hexanol, 1-octanol, and 1-nonanol. Fig. 7 shows the corresponding results for 1-nonanol and 1-decanol. Additionally, the AADs for the density ρ , the thermal expansion coefficient α , and the isothermal compressibility β , i.e. $\text{AAD}_{Y, \text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$, were calculated for the four EOS and five substances. For the density ρ , the experimental data from this work were used. For the thermal expansion coefficient α and the isothermal compressibility β , the pseudo-experimental data from this work were used (see above). Fig. 8 shows the AADs for ρ , α , and β for all substances and EOS.

Figure 6: Relative deviation between the results for the density from the four EOS frameworks and the empirical correlations from this work (cf. Eq. (3)) for 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, and 1-octanol as a function of the pressure p . Each row shows results for a constant temperature.

Figure 7: Relative deviation between the results for the density from the four EOS frameworks and the empirical correlations from this work (cf. Eq. (3)) for 1-nonanol and 1-decanol as a function of the pressure p . Each rows shows results for a constant temperature.

Figure 8: Average absolute deviation of the EOS results $AAD_{Y,EOS}^{\text{th}}$ (cf. Eq. (9)) for the density ρ , the thermal expansion coefficient α , and the isothermal compressibility β for the five 1-alcohols. The AADs were computed with respect to the reference data from this work 'th'.

The findings for all five alcohols are similar. First of all, the deviations for the EOS are overall about an order of magnitude larger than the deviations for the empirical correlations for describing the experimental data, cf. Figs. 4 and 5. In the entire considered temperature and pressure range, the deviations for the density are in the range $\pm 3\%$ for all EOS and substances. Also, the EOS-deviations of the second-order derivative properties α and β are about one order of magnitude larger than the deviations obtained for the density, which is, among other reasons, due to larger uncertainties of the pseudo-experimental data of α and β (up to 14 %, see above). For both second-order derivative properties, the deviations reach values up to 50 % across all studied EOS frameworks – yet with significant differences between the individual EOS frameworks.

The PC-SAFT results overestimate the density for most substances and states, cf. Figs. 6 and 7. While the density results of the PC-SAFT EOS often agree well with the experimental data at ambient pressure, the density is overestimated at elevated pressure. The thermal expansion coefficient, a measure for the temperature dependence of the density, is well described by the PC-SAFT EOS with $\text{AAD}_{\alpha,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ values between 4 % and 10 % (cf. Fig. 8 middle). The pressure dependence of the density, i.e. the isothermal compressibility β , is less accurately described by the PC-SAFT EOS (cf. Fig. 8 bottom). The $\text{AAD}_{\beta,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ for the PC-SAFT EOS is the second largest of the different EOS and increases with increasing chain length with values from 18 % (1-hexanol) up to 36 % (1-decanol).

The SAFT-VR Mie EOS yields the lowest deviations among the studied EOS for the density for all studied substances with a lowest $\text{AAD}_{\rho,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ of $< 0.2\%$ and a maximum $\text{AAD}_{\rho,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ of around 0.7 % (cf. Fig. 8 top). This is also reflected in the deviations for α and β . Similar to the PC-SAFT EOS, the SAFT-VR Mie EOS provides a good description of the thermal expansion coefficient α , which is line with findings from previous studies.^{133,134} Only for 1-hexanol and 1-heptanol, the $\text{AAD}_{\alpha,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ obtained from the SAFT-VR Mie EOS is relatively large with values up to 14 % (for 1-hexanol). The pressure dependence of the density, i.e. the isothermal compressibility, of the alcohols is described remarkably well by the SAFT-VR Mie

EOS (cf. Fig. 8 bottom). The values for the $\text{AAD}_{\beta,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ are the smallest for all substances with a maximum of 10 %. The good performance of the SAFT-VR Mie EOS is probably to some extent due to the fact that a higher degree of freedom was used in the fitting procedure since the additional parameter λ_r is used in the models. However, increasing the repulsive exponent λ_r in force fields yields similar improvements for the description of the density and the pressure dependence of the density.^{135,136}

The performance of the soft SAFT EOS for describing the density is similar to the performance of PC-SAFT. Only for the density of 1-heptanol and 1-nonanol, the deviations obtained for the soft SAFT EOS are significantly larger than those of the PC-SAFT, cf. Fig. 8 top. The density is overestimated by the soft SAFT EOS for most of the substances and conditions, especially for the lower temperatures (cf. Figs. 6 and 7). This is also reflected in the deviations obtained by soft SAFT for the thermal expansion coefficient α , which are slightly larger than those obtained from the PC-SAFT and SAFT-VR Mie EOS. The pressure dependence of the density is slightly overestimated by the soft SAFT EOS (similar to the PC-SAFT) yielding $\text{AAD}_{\beta,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$ between 9 % and 28 %.

The results from the CPA EOS show the largest deviations for all three properties (cf. Fig. 8): The CPA EOS yields the largest deviations for the density with values $\text{AAD}_{\rho,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}} > 1\%$ for all substances (see Fig. 8 top). At ambient conditions ($T = 298.15\text{ K}$ and $p = 0.1\text{ MPa}$), the deviations for the density are relatively small (see Figs. 6 and 7). At high temperatures, the density at ambient pressure is overestimated with deviations of more than 2 % by the CPA EOS. The AAD for describing the thermal expansion coefficient by the CPA EOS, i.e. $\text{AAD}_{\alpha,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$, is the largest among the studied EOS with values between 35 % and more than 50 % (cf. Fig. 8 middle). Also, the pressure dependency of the density (cf. Fig. 8 bottom) is not well reproduced by the CPA EOS: The slope $\partial\rho/\partial p$ is too small (cf. Figs. 6 and 7), i.e. the CPA EOS underestimates the isothermal compressibility β . This results in large $\text{AAD}_{\text{EOS},\beta}^{\text{th}}$ values of up to 35 %. The overall relatively high deviations obtained for the CPA EOS are possibly due to the fact that the molecule elongation is not explicitly

represented in the CPA EOS.

Overall, there is a tendency for the deviations to increase with increasing chain length of the 1-alcohols, i.e. the smallest deviations are observed for 1-hexanol and the largest deviations are observed for 1-decanol. This is the case for the CPA EOS for all three studied properties (ρ , α , β) and the case for PC-SAFT and soft SAFT for one or two properties. This indicates that the chain contribution (which is coupled with the monomer contribution^{39,41,42}) causes systematic deviations and that the molecular structure is not ideally described by it. Only for the SAFT-VR Mie EOS, no systematic deviations are obtained for the molecule size dependency. This is in line with the fact that the lowest overall deviations were obtained for the SAFT-VR Mie EOS.

We have also evaluated the extrapolation behavior of the EOS models by studying the characteristic curves and assessing the behavior in the vapor-liquid two-phase region. Fig. 9 shows the characteristic curve results for 1-octanol for the PC-SAFT, SAFT-VR Mie, soft SAFT, and CPA EOS. 1-Octanol was chosen as an example here; The results for the other

Figure 9: Characteristic curves of 1-octanol obtained from the PC-SAFT EOS, SAFT-VR Mie EOS, soft SAFT EOS, and CPA EOS (left to right) including the Zeno curve (red), Amagat curve (orange), Boyle curve (blue), and Charles curve (purple). Black solid line and star represents the vapor pressure curve and the critical point, respectively, as calculated by the corresponding EOS.

studied 1-alcohols are qualitatively the same (see Supporting Information). The SAFT-VR Mie EOS yields realistic predictions of all four characteristic curves. The other three EOS frameworks yield realistic Zeno, Charles, and Boyle curves, but a distorted Amagat

curve. These findings are in line with the performance of the four EOS frameworks reported for other substances.^{137–139} For the PC-SAFT EOS, the distorted Amagat curve has been attributed to the employed soft repulsion in the monomer term.¹³⁹ For the soft SAFT, a distorted Amagat curve has also been attributed to the underlying monomer term,¹³⁷ i.e. the Johnson Lennard-Jones EOS.⁵³ Hence, for both PC-SAFT and soft SAFT, the defects in the Amagat curve are a result of the monomer term. Since all four EOS frameworks applied in this work use the SAFT term for describing the H-bonding association and a thermodynamically consistent Amagat curve is obtained for the SAFT-VR Mie EOS, the SAFT term does most likely not contribute to the defects in the depicted case. Since the CPA EOS comprises only the SAFT term and the Soave-Redlich-Kwong term, the latter probably causes the defects in the Amagat curve. Hence, among the studied models, only the SAFT-VR Mie EOS should be used for extrapolation to extreme states.

We have also tested the extrapolation behavior in the vapor-liquid metastable and unstable region. A physically reasonable behavior, i.e. a single spinodal and no undulations of isotherms and a smooth van der Waals loop, is for example critical for the application of an EOS model within density gradient theory for describing interfacial properties.^{140?,141} The results for 1-octanol from the SAFT-VR Mie EOS are depicted in Fig. 10. Additionally, isotherms are depicted, where density data were determined in this work. The SAFT-VR Mie EOS yields a single smooth van der Waals loops in a wide temperature range for 1-octanol. This is in line with results reported in Ref.³⁰ for the underlying monomer.

Conclusions

In this work, the density of the 1-alcohols 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol, 1-octanol, 1-nonanol, and 1-decanol was measured at pressures up to 120 MPa with a high pressure vibrating-tube densimeter. The available density data for the five 1-alcohols was significantly extended and supplemented by this work – especially at elevated temperatures and pressures. Based on

Figure 10: Density of 1-octanol as function of the pressure for ten isotherms between 323.15 K and 1023.15 K. Lines are results from the SAFT-VR Mie EOS: Black solid line, black dashed line, and star represents the vapor-liquid equilibrium curve, the spinodal curve, and the critical point, respectively; colored lines are isotherms with the color coded according to the color scale. The squares are the experimental results from this work.

that experimental data, an empirical correlations was developed that describes the data with an accuracy of 0.05 %. This was used to determine pseudo-experimental data for the thermal expansion coefficient and the isothermal compressibility.

The density, the thermal expansion coefficient, and the isothermal compressibility were modeled using molecular-based EOS, namely the PC-SAFT, SAFT-VR Mie, soft SAFT, and CPA. Therefore, new parameter sets were fitted using the new experimental data from this work in combination with vapor-liquid equilibrium data from the literature. Overall, the SAFT-VR Mie EOS yields the best results: i) It is the most accurate model for describing the density, the thermal expansion coefficient, and the isothermal compressibility and at the same time describes the vapor-liquid equilibrium data very well; ii) it yields a thermodynamically consistent extrapolation behavior regarding Brown's curves as well as into the vapor-liquid two-phase region. Yet, the deviations are about an order of magnitude larger compared to the uncertainty of the experimental data.

Appendix - AAD of EOS Models

Table 9 reports the results of the fits of the component-specific models developed in this work for the vapor pressure, the saturated density, and the homogeneous state liquid density. The AADs are calculated using the data used for the fit, which comprise literature data for the vapor pressure and saturated liquid density as well as the measured densities from this work. Details on the fitting procedure are given in the main text.

Table 9: Result of the fit: Deviations of the EOS models to the reference data used for the fit for the vapor pressure $\text{AAD}_{p^s,\text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}}$, the saturated liquid densities $\text{AAD}_{\rho^s,\text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}}$, and the homogeneous state liquid density $\text{AAD}_{\rho,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}}$.

	1-hexanol	1-heptanol	1-octanol	1-nonanol	1-decanol
$\text{AAD}_{p^s,\text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}} / \%$					
PC-SAFT	0.31	0.84	0.98	0.74	0.92
SAFT-VR Mie	0.21	0.77	0.99	0.99	1.24
soft SAFT	0.37	0.7	0.92	1.16	1.4
CPA	0.49	0.88	0.94	0.51	0.93
$\text{AAD}_{\rho^s,\text{EOS}}^{\text{lit}} / \%$					
PC-SAFT	0.76	0.41	0.56	0.65	0.73
SAFT-VR Mie	0.92	0.56	0.24	0.51	0.65
soft SAFT	1.3	1.68	1.2	2.11	1.67
CPA	1.11	1.39	1.59	1.45	1.25
$\text{AAD}_{\rho,\text{EOS}}^{\text{th}} / \%$					
PC-SAFT	0.49	0.57	0.66	0.91	0.99
SAFT-VR Mie	0.4	0.31	0.2	0.38	0.73
soft SAFT	0.61	0.97	0.61	1.59	0.93
CPA	1.13	1.34	1.37	1.54	1.52

Associated Content

Supporting Information

PDF file (Multi-parameter EOS of Calibration Fluids, Parameters of Empirical Correlations $\rho_{\text{corr}}(T, p)$, Literature Data, EOS Parameter from the Literature, Brown's Characteristic

Curves); CSV file (Pseudo-experimental data of the thermal expansion coefficient and the isothermal compressibility)

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Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101137725 (BatCAT) and from the KSB Foundation - project 1385. The authors thank Rebecca Loubet and Jens Wagner for their support in carrying out the experimental work.

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